

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No1
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 326 sahifa,
5-yanvar, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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IMPROVING THE THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR INTEGRATING GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES INTO ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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UDK: 37.013.378.096.378.22

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayoniga generativ sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini integratsiya qilish metodikasini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda sun'iy intellektga asoslangan ta'lim vositalarining lingvodidaktik imkoniyatlari, ularning o'quv jarayonidagi funksional roli hamda talabalarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi samaradorligi ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan asoslanadi. Shuningdek, generativ sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini qo'llashda metodik yondashuvlar, didaktik tamoyillar va pedagogik shart-sharoitlar tizimli ravishda yoritib beriladi.

Key words: generativ sun'iy intellekt, ingliz tilini o'qitish metodikasi, oliy ta'lim, raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari, lingvodidaktika, kommunikativ kompetensiya, innovatsion pedagogika.

Annotatsiya: This article examines the theoretical foundations for developing methodologies aimed at integrating generative artificial intelligence technologies into English language teaching in higher education. The study explores the linguodidactic potential of AI-based educational tools, their functional role in the instructional process, and their effectiveness in enhancing students' communicative competence. Furthermore, the paper systematically analyzes methodological approaches, didactic principles, and pedagogical conditions necessary for the effective implementation of generative artificial intelligence technologies in language education.

Kalit so'zlar: generative artificial intelligence, English language teaching methodology, higher education, digital educational technologies, linguodidactics, communicative competence, innovative pedagogy.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются теоретические основы развития методики интеграции генеративных технологий искусственного интеллекта в процесс обучения английскому языку в высших учебных заведениях. Анализируются лингводидактические возможности инструментов искусственного интеллекта, их функциональная роль в образовательном процессе, а также влияние на формирование коммуникативной компетентности обучающихся. Особое внимание уделяется методическим подходам, дидактическим принципам и педагогическим условиям эффективного применения генеративных технологий искусственного интеллекта в языковом образовании.

Ключевые слова: генеративный искусственный интеллект, методика обучения английскому языку, высшее образование, цифровые образовательные технологии, лингводидактика, коммуникативная компетентность, инновационная педагогика.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of contemporary globalization and digitalization, the higher education system is undergoing an intensive process of transformation. This process necessitates the renewal of educational content, the improvement of teaching methodologies, and the integration of modern pedagogical technologies into educational practice. In particular, the growing demand for innovative digital tools in foreign language instruction, especially in English language education, has become increasingly evident. From this perspective, the integration of generative artificial intelligence technologies into the educational process is advancing English language teaching methodology to a new stage of development. These technologies function as a significant pedagogical factor in individualizing the learning process, enhancing students' autonomous learning activities, and developing their communicative competence. The digital learning environment facilitated by generative artificial intelligence supports the formation of personalized learning trajectories and elevates the quality of interaction between instructors and students to a qualitatively new level.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In contemporary pedagogical research, the integration of intelligent technologies into the educational process is closely associated with enhancing educational effectiveness, individualizing learning activities, and developing students' autonomous learning skills. In particular, the use of generative artificial intelligence technologies in foreign language instruction, especially in English language teaching, is increasingly regarded as a significant pedagogical factor that enables the orientation of language learning toward communicative and reflective activities. Therefore, the incorporation of these technologies into teaching methodology requires a solid theoretical and methodological foundation.

According to the sociocultural approach proposed by Lev Vygotsky, which emphasizes the decisive role of social interaction and communication in the educational process, knowledge is constructed through interpersonal interaction, and a learning environment adapted to learners' developmental needs is of critical importance. These theoretical assumptions provide a foundation for understanding the pedagogical effectiveness of dialogic and interactive learning environments facilitated by generative artificial intelligence. Flexible learning environments supported by artificial intelligence tools promote students' active engagement in communication and contribute to the development of their communicative competence. Within the framework of constructivist learning theory, priority is given to the independent construction of knowledge through learners' active participation rather than the passive reception of ready-made information. According to the views of Jerome Bruner, learning becomes effective only when it is grounded in inquiry, analysis, and the resolution of problem situations. Generative artificial intelligence technologies support this form of constructive activity by enabling students to generate texts, model dialogues, and articulate independent ideas.

In his extensive analysis of factors influencing educational effectiveness, John Hattie emphasizes that continuous and high-quality feedback plays a crucial role in improving learning outcomes. The capacity of generative artificial intelligence technologies to perform automated analysis, identify errors, and provide individualized recommendations creates favorable conditions for the practical implementation of this theoretical perspective in English language teaching. Within the competency-based approach, educational outcomes are assessed not only in terms of the volume of acquired knowledge but also according to the extent to which this knowledge can be applied in real-life contexts. The scholarly works of Robert Marzano substantiate the necessity of ensuring the integrated development of knowledge, skills, and attitudes within the educational process. English language instruction organized through the use of generative artificial intelligence contributes to the comprehensive development of students' linguistic, communicative, and cognitive competencies.

Albert Bandura's social learning theory, which conceptualizes learning as a developmental process shaped by observation and reflection, also constitutes an important theoretical foundation for the present study. The modeling, example-based learning, and self-analysis features inherent in generative artificial intelligence technologies foster the development of students' reflective thinking. The analysis of the aforementioned theoretical perspectives indicates that methodologies for integrating generative artificial intelligence technologies into English language teaching in higher education are grounded in sociocultural, constructivist, competency-based, and digital pedagogy approaches. These technologies enable the individualization of the educational process, active student engagement in communication, and the development of reflective and autonomous learning skills. Consequently, the methodologically sound implementation of generative artificial intelligence technologies in English language teaching plays a significant role in achieving qualitatively new pedagogical outcomes and ensuring the innovative development of the higher education system.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Generative artificial intelligence technologies represent one of the most advanced domains of artificial intelligence, with their primary function being the creation of new content tailored to users' needs. In the educational process, these technologies enable the automatic generation of texts, dialogues, test tasks, linguistic exercises, and multimodal learning materials. From a pedagogical perspective, the advantages of generative artificial intelligence are manifested in its adaptability, interactivity, and reflective capabilities. Specifically, these technologies design educational content in accordance with students' levels of knowledge, language competence, and individual learning pace. As a result, the educational process shifts from a standardized approach to an individualized and learner-centered model. Furthermore, generative artificial intelligence serves as an effective tool for developing students' metacognitive activity, fostering self-assessment skills, and enhancing analytical abilities. This, in turn, ensures that education is oriented not only toward knowledge transmission but also toward comprehensive personal development.

In the context of English language teaching, generative artificial intelligence technologies offer a wide range of didactic opportunities. In particular, these technologies make it possible to model communicative situations that closely resemble real-life contexts, actively engage students in interaction, and develop their speaking competence. Moreover, by automatically generating academic and professionally oriented texts, generative artificial intelligence facilitates the integration of English language learning with professional activities. This contributes to students' acquisition of language skills based on practical needs. Through the automatic analysis of written and spoken language, identification of errors, and provision of corrective feedback, generative artificial intelligence promotes the development of reflective thinking. Consequently, students acquire the ability to independently analyze and improve their own language performance, thereby ensuring sustainable and high-quality outcomes in the process of learning English. The methodology for integrating generative artificial intelligence technologies into English language teaching is grounded in several contemporary pedagogical approaches. In particular, the competency-based approach aims to align language learning outcomes with real communicative activities and focuses on developing students' functional language competence. The learner-centered approach emphasizes the consideration of individual differences and the creation of a learning environment tailored to students' personal needs and interests. The constructivist approach, in turn, prioritizes the active involvement of learners in constructing knowledge independently rather than receiving it in a ready-made form. The digital pedagogy approach views generative artificial intelligence technologies as an integral component of the modern digital learning environment and emphasizes their alignment with clearly defined didactic objectives.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development of methodologies for integrating generative artificial intelligence technologies into English language teaching in higher education requires a theoretically grounded, systematic, and comprehensive approach. These technologies serve as an important pedagogical resource for updating the content and structure of the educational process, as well as for individualizing instruction and enhancing interactivity. Educational processes organized on the basis of generative artificial intelligence contribute to the development of students' communicative, linguistic, and cognitive competencies, thereby enabling qualitatively new outcomes in English language teaching. Therefore, the methodologically sound implementation of these technologies plays a significant role in the innovative development of the higher education system.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №1

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.